

EFFECTS OF LED LIGHTS USED FOR GROWING LETTUCE UNDER CONTROLLED ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS: A REVIEW

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Abstract

In today's world, pursuing food security and expanding food availability are critical aspirations for countries of varying economic statuses. The agricultural sector plays a vital role in addressing these challenges, and researchers have introduced a modern approach utilizing LED technology to enhance plant growth and metabolic processes in a controlled environment. However, the lack of light intensity and limited spectrum can negatively impact our plants. To overcome this, scientists have developed an innovative solution that uses LED technology to improve plant growth and metabolic processes. A recent study delved into the effects of different light spectrums, including white, UV, red, far red, red/blue, blue, and green, on physiological parameters, bioactive materials, and nutritional composition in various lettuce cultivars. While previous research has focused on growth, quality, and bioactivity, it is essential to investigate the nutritional content of these cultivars as interest in our food's nutritional value grows. By examining the nutritional content of hydroponically grown lettuce cultivars, we can make strides toward a more sustainable and healthier future.

Keywords: LED Lighting, Lettuce Growth, Controlled Environment Agriculture, Photosynthesis Efficiency, Plant Morphology.

INTRODUCTION

As the global population grows, food supply and security concerns have become increasingly urgent (Alabi, & Ngwenyama, 2023; Mbow et al., 2020; Hemathilake, & Gunathilake, 2022). In response, plant factories with artificial light (PFALs) have emerged as a promising solution to provide year-round crops with consistent taste, shape, and safety (Kozai & Niu, 2020; Csambalik et al., 2023). By creating suitable environments for growth and development, PFALs can optimize plant growth parameters, such as light, air temperature, humidity, and gas composition (Bantis et al., 2024). Unlike traditional open fields and greenhouse farming, PFALs can provide optimal environments for plants regardless of the outdoor background (Boros, et al., 2023). In PFALs, artificial lighting sources such as fluorescent lights and light-emitting diodes (LEDs) are used for their superior efficiency in converting electrical energy into radiation (Sharma, et al., 2024).

LEDs, in particular, have drawn significant attention due to their extensive control over spectrum and intensity (Kozai, et al., 2021; Paucek et al., 2020). The annual lettuce plant (*Lactuca sativa L.*) belongs to the family Asteraceae and is primarily farmed as a leafy vegetable. It is a significant vegetable worldwide (Nasih et al., 2022). Due to their high concentration of fiber, folate, carotenoids, phenolic and antioxidant chemicals, minerals, and vitamins A, C, and K, leafy vegetables like lettuce (*Lactuca sativa L.*) are regarded as being healthful (Camejo et al., 2020). When the total weight of a plant is considered, lettuce ranks fourth in terms of its overall contribution to nutrition, after tomatoes, citrus, and potatoes (Mohamed et al., 2022). In Malaysia, the most prevalent varieties of lettuce include Crisphead (also known as iceberg), romaine, butterhead, and looseleaf (green or red coral). However, despite their commonality, there are significant differences in their growth habits, leaf colours, shapes, and textures.

Figure 1: Types of lettuce: Crisphead, Butterhead, Looseleaf, and Romaine.

It is worth noting that lettuce is a highly diverse crop, with variations in its physical characteristics and nutritional composition. Hence, selecting the appropriate variety for cultivation should take into account factors such as environmental conditions, market demand, and consumer preferences. Additionally, growers should consider factors such as yield potential, disease resistance, and post-harvest quality to ensure the profitability and sustainability of their lettuce production. Lettuce, a leafy green vegetable commonly used in salads, is a versatile ingredient that can be incorporated into various dishes to derive health benefits. One can enjoy lettuce in numerous ways, such as in wraps, sandwiches, egg rolls, spring rolls, rice dishes, tacos, smoothies, and more, depending

on the type of lettuce. Additionally, certain types of lettuce can even serve as a substitute for bread in selected sandwiches or burgers. By experimenting with the incorporation of lettuce into diverse dishes, one can enjoy its nutritional advantages while adding variety to their diet.

Vertical Farming

Vertical farming presents a sustainable solution to the economic and ecological challenges of traditional food production methods. This innovative approach involves cultivating crops in multi-level buildings or warehouses, utilizing vertical space to increase yields. By adopting this method, we can conserve energy, water, and fossil fuels while reducing transportation requirements and minimizing the use of pesticides and other potentially hazardous chemicals. Vertical farming can help address the pressing issues of food security, climate change, and environmental degradation while promoting economic growth and social well-being. This is achieved through the use of three main technological approaches: Aquaponics, Aeroponics, and Hydroponics.

Aquaponics

This system integrates water and fish into a single ecosystem. Fish waste is used to nourish hydroponic production beds, providing sustainable fertilizer. Nutrient-rich waste produced by fish is natural feed for plants in vertical farms. The plant beds provide a thriving environment for the plants and play a vital role in purifying and filtering the wastewater, acting as 'biofilters,' and returning clean water to the fishponds (Miliauskienė et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2023). Although Aquaponics has shown promising results, it is still in the experimental phase, so it has yet to be implemented on a large-scale commercial level. However, it is worth considering as a sustainable and eco-friendly method of farming that can potentially revolutionize the food industry (Bradu et al., 2023; Rebouh et al., 2023).

Figure 2: Aquaponic graphic illustration from the National Center for Appropriate Technology (NCAT).

Aeroponics

NASA's pioneering work in developing aeroponics has enabled us to overcome the challenges of growing plants in space. Unlike traditional Hydroponics, this method enables speedy plant growth in a soil-free atmosphere of mist and air. This method uses 90% less water than efficient hydroponics and does not need water-holding trays (Shivalingaiah, 2020). Plants grown using this method can be cultivated in a broader range of spaces, from basements to warehouses, and they have the potential to be more nutritious (De-Bernardi- et al., 2020).

Hydroponics

Vertical farming has revolutionized how we grow crops, and hydroponics has played a pivotal role in making it possible. It uses water and mineral solutions instead of soil or gravel to grow plants. The nutrient solution submerges the roots and can be monitored and circulated using intelligent systems. Soil-based agriculture can be labour-intensive due to weeding, tilling, and removing dirt. It also involves the use of pesticides and results in nitrogen wastes (Maurya et al., 2023).

Figure 3: Hydroponic graphic illustration: NCAT

This literature review carefully organizes information on lettuce and hydroponic systems, specifically focusing on the conditions needed for microgreens. The researchers are optimistic that their findings will enable them to meet the growing demand for sustainable and efficient food production. By optimizing the production of lettuce microgreens, we can promote healthier eating habits and contribute to a more sustainable future.

Light Emission Diode (LEDs)

In agriculture, visible light is just as crucial for plant growth and development as it is for photosynthesis. Its importance is overlooked in other food processing fields, though. Several crops can maintain their postharvest quality in low light by delaying senescence

and improving phytochemical and nutritional quality (Paradiso, & Proietti, 2022; Pierik, & Ballaré, 2021). LED Light is a relief from the sun, essential for plant growth (Zhang, et al., 2020). As a vast band, natural light emits energy from multiple wavelength ranges. Some narrow bands, such as blue and red, serve as the underpinning of immersion bands for developing plant growth and physiology. Light quality or spectrum assessments are relatively delicate compared to light intensity or photoperiod studies. Concerns about energy effectiveness, agricultural inputs' environmental effects, and food security in product systems have lately increased (Wang, 2022). LEDs aren't only a practical kind of lighting because of their reduced energy consumption, but they also produce lower heat, which means lower energy is consumed to cool greenhouse cultivation, greenhouses, and plant factories (Pachapur et al., 2020). LEDs' monochromic nature offers crops with targeted and high-quality irradiation at applicable wavelengths, performing lower energy use for growing crops. Likewise, the rising operation of LEDs in controlled surrounding and shuttered plant production systems enables crop products to continue constantly, independent of external weather conditions (Engler, & Krarti, 2021; Ahamed et al., 2023).

As a result, LEDs are anticipated to become a light source with a significant pledge for high-power illumination in agricultural activities. With the preface of LEDs, there has been an increase in studies towards commercial plant cultivation. Several studies have been conducted to probe the impact of various LED colours and fusions of fluorescent lights on agricultural yields (Zissis et al., 2021; Mahto et al., 2021). Some of the crops that have formerly been grown using LED irradiation include lettuce (Alrajhi, et al., 2023), pepper (Azad, et al., 2020), wheat (Ginzburg, & Klein, 2020), spinach (Gómez, & Jiménez, 2020; Zou et al., 2021) and banana (Boros et al., 2023). Lately, as compared to a greenhouse or field-grown equivalents, herbs such as mint and basil, as well as pot flowers such as petunia, primula, marigold, and stock, were produced under LED irradiation with good marketability qualities (Maunder, 2022).

In plant cells, phytochromes red-light receptors and cryptochromes blue-light receptors are the key receptors responsible for photomorphogenic responses. The mechanism of signal transduction through these receptors remains a mystery, although they are believed to be involved in cellular protein-protein interactions. As a result, exposure to specific wavelengths of light can ultimately lead to changes in the position of light-signalling proteins, modifications in ion homeostasis, gene expression, and other crucial cellular processes (Babla, et al., 2023).

Types of LED Lights

Over the past decade, the lighting used in controlled-environment agriculture has undergone significant advancements, thanks to the improved energy efficiency, spectral tuning, and design of LED fixtures. As a result, LED fixtures have become increasingly popular in indoor vertical farms, with growers having a wide range of fixtures to choose from, each with its own specifications.

Figure 4: Six different light spectrum treatments in a growth room from red (R), blue, red & far-red (B/R/FR), red/blue (R/B), warm-white (W), blue, green & red (B/G/R) and/or blue (B), LEDs (Qingwu & Runkle 2022).

When selecting a fixture, factors such as cost, photosynthetic photon efficiency, photon spectrum, form factor, and light responses of crops must be taken into account (Kusuma et al., 2020) While red/blue LEDs are commonly used in horticultural applications due to their high photon and photosynthetic efficiency (Kusuma et al., 2020), broad-spectrum LEDs also have their advantages. By adding green light to red/blue light, white light is created in the human eye, revealing the true colors of plants and making it easier for workers to inspect crop growth, nutrient conditions, insects, and diseases in an aesthetically pleasing environment. Although broad-spectrum LEDs decrease the photosynthetic photon efficiency compared to red/blue LEDs, high color fidelity under broad-spectrum LED lighting can be especially desirable in indoor vertical farms (Babla et al., 2023). White (LEDs) have become increasingly popular due to their long lifespan, high efficiency, and low energy consumption. While it is possible to create white light by combining monochromatic blue, green, and red LEDs, commercial white LEDs are typically blue LEDs coated with a phosphor. This coating converts most blue photons to longer wavelengths, such as green, red, and far red, which in turn emit a broad range of biologically active radiation (Bispo-Jr et al., 2021). The material and amount of phosphor coatings determine the hue of the white LED, as indicated by the correlated color temperature (CCT). Warm-white LEDs, with a low percentage of blue light (e.g., 7%), have a lower CCT of 2500 to 3500 K.

In contrast, neutral-white (3500 to 4500 K), cool-white (4500 to 5500 K), and daylight (5500 to 7500 K) LEDs have higher percentages of blue light (e.g., 20% and 30%, respectively) and higher photon efficiencies (Cope & Bugbee, 2013; Kusuma et al., 2020). White LEDs also differ in their ability to reveal the true colors of plants, as indicated by the color rendering index (CRI) or the TM-30 fidelity index (Rf). Higher indices indicate higher color fidelity. In addition, specialized white LEDs, such as mint-white (equalized-white) LEDs, have efficient green phosphor coatings that enable them to create high-CRI white light when combined with red LEDs.

Developed by OSRAM Opto Semiconductors, these LEDs are blue LEDs coated with an efficient green phosphor (Ma et al., 2021). In conclusion, the ability of white LEDs to emit different hues of light and their varying abilities to reveal the true colors of plants make them versatile and useful lighting options. The material and amount of phosphor coatings, as well as the correlated color temperature and color rendering index, are important factors to consider when selecting the appropriate white LED for a particular application.

Light Mechanism in Plants

Intricate mechanisms allow plants to absorb electromagnetic radiation in a range of spectrum areas. Moreover, the spectrum of sunlight that is capable of photosynthesis (400-700 nm) is notably absorbed by chlorophyll pigments, which powers the process by which plants turn carbon dioxide and water into oxygen and carbohydrates. Likewise, the energy necessary for life on our planet is derived from the carbon that is absorbed during photosynthesis (Roeber et al., 2021).

The impact of light on plants is truly remarkable, as it activates a surplus of crucial physiological responses, including seed germination, phototropism, chloroplast movement, shadow avoidance, circadian measures, unfolding time, and morphogenesis. In addition, light also serves as the primary energy source for photosynthesis, enabling plants to generate their own food (Ptushenko, et al., 2020). Plants can detect changes in light and change their shape without affecting photosynthesis. This is known as photomorphogenesis.

During the process of photomorphogenesis, the photoreceptors present in lower plants perceive photons from various spectral areas. One such light detector of immense significance is phytochrome, which can detect both red and far-red light (Upadhyay, 2020). The light spectrum has a significant impact on plant processes. Phytochromes, which are photoreceptors, are ideal for detecting weak signals. The colour that regulates photomorphogenesis and has garnered the most scientific attention is Phytochrome due to its sensitivity (Burgie et al., 2021; Ptushenko et al., 2020).

A practical method for illustrating the influence of light on plant growth involves exposing leaves to various hues.

Figure 5: A schematic diagram representing different colour light treatments and their effects on plants (Rehman et al., 2020).

The significance of light in facilitating a plant's energy production through photosynthesis is well-established (Landi, et al., 2020). However, it should be noted that not all wavelengths of light are equally beneficial for the growth and development of plants. Specifically, the red, blue, and yellow spectrums are considered ideal owing to their optimal absorption by the plant's pigments. Interestingly, plants exhibit a distinctive green hue despite not absorbing green light. This is because they reflect green wavelengths, which accounts for their distinct colouration.

Effects of Blue, Green, Red, and Far-red LEDs on Lettuce Plant Growth

Adding far-red light enriched root and shoot development and leaf area index (Pierik, & Ballaré, 2021; Sytar, et al., 2021). Also, far-red has demonstrated a significant influence on lettuce growth and development, raising the number of leaves and broadening the leaf and stem in red and baby leaf lettuce (Huber et al., 2020; Li & Roeber et al., 2021) which leads to a rise in biomass (Antar, et al., 2021). Furthermore, while sustaining a steady level of red light, high-intensity green LED light hastens lettuce growth (Shah et al., 2020; Destek et al., 2021), as divergent to blue light, which gives lettuce seedlings their compacted shape (Cammarisano, et al., 2022). Certainly, Light is critical for plant growth. Blue, green, and red light affect stem length, while UV light intensity affects leaf growth. Reduced light intensity leads to poor plant growth (Jingga et al., 2022a). Treatment with red-and-blue LEDs improved the morphology of lettuce (Chen et al., 2022a). In contrast

to earlier studies (Nguyen et al., 2021) weighing the treatment with a specialized white LED light that increased the plant growth and yield, there was a recognized decrease in plant growth. Indoor hydroponic lettuce plants treated with blue/red LEDs are more aesthetically pleasing than those cultivated in greenhouses or with standard LED setups (Rasool, 2020).

The rise in fresh weight of various lettuce cultivars was then noticed after exposure to far-red light (Legendre, et al., 2021). UVA light makes lettuce cultivars' fresh weight rise (Kong, & Nemali, 2021). Additionally, it has been noted that red light and green light might increase the fresh weight of lettuce (Li, et al., 2021). Blue light encourages the growth of biomass in red-leaf lettuce seedlings (Liu, & van Iersel 2022; Jin et al., 2021). Plants under R-LED produced long leaf lengths and higher fresh weight compared to other treatments, with Blue LED having the lowest (Lee et al., 2023).

Table 1: Effect of LEDs on the physiological aspect of lettuce plant

S/N	Light Colour	Plant	Effect on Physiological Aspect	Reference
1.	Red LED Blue LED	Mini Red Romaine Lettuce (cv Breen)	Plants under R-LED produced long leaf length higher fresh weight compared to other treatment with Blue LED having the lowest.	(Lee et al., 2023)
2.	Blue/Red 130 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-2}$ Blue/Red 389 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-2}$	Red Lettuce Batavia cv (Blackhawk)	BR 130 produces less plant biomass than BR 389, indicating that BR 389 treatment is more effective.	(Modarelli et al., 2022)
3.	UV LEDs 450 nm-660 nm	Red Lettuce	Different colors of light affect stem length and UV light intensity influences leaf growth. Lower light intensity can lead to poor plant growth.	(Jingga et al., 2022b)
4.	Red/Blue (L16-L96 and D8-D48)	Butter leaf lettuce	The procedure was brief. The treatments had an impact on the morphology of the lettuce.	(Chen et al., 2022b)
5.	SWL 1 and 2 437 nm	Butterhead Lettuce Romaine Lettuce	The two lettuce plants grew more after treatment with SWL 1 and 2 than under RB.	(Nguyen et al., 2021)
6.	Blue 440 nm	Lettuce (<i>L. sativa</i> var foliosum cv. Dubacek and <i>L. sativa</i> , 'Michalina')	small-scale plant morphology	(Sergejeva et al., 2018)
7.	Far-red 700–850 nm	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>) 'Frillice Crisp'	Far-red light addition enhanced fresh weight.	(Tan et al., 2022)
8.	Blue/red LEDs	lettuce plants (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> cv. Grizzly)	These plants have more aesthetic appeal than those grown in greenhouses or under conventional LED setups.	(Verdegaal, 2021)
9.	Far-red 700–850 nm	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.) 'Frillice Crisp'	Far-red light increased leaf area index and may have reduced dry weight content by 27-7% due to accelerated growth.	(Shmarev et al., 2024)

10.	Far-red 700–850 nm	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> Sunmang) seedlings from 16 days-old	Improved root and shoot development	(Zou, et al., 2021)
11.	Far-red 700–850 nm	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> var. <i>crispa</i>) 'Green Oak Leaf'	White LEDs alone caused a 36% reduction in shoot fresh weight, and the plants looked scarce and twisted.	(Jovine, (2021)
12.	Far-red 700–850 nm	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>) 'Sunmang' seedling from 16 days- old	a higher fresh weight	(Chen, et al., 2021)
13.	Far-red 700–850 nm	Red lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>) 'Sunmang'	There were more leaves, and they were longer.	(Smirnov, et al., 2022)
14.	Green 490 – 550 nm	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>) cultivars, red leaf Sunmang' and green leaf 'Grand Rapid' 18day seedlings for 4 weeks	Using green LEDs instead of blue ones while keeping the same amount of red LEDs led to a 61% increase in the fresh weight of red leaf lettuce shoots.	(Spalholz et al., 2020)
15.	Far-red 700–850 nm	Red lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.) 'Sunmang'	When R/FR was 1:2, fresh and dry weight were at their maximum levels.	(Madar, & Hájos, 2022).
16.	Green 490 – 550 nm	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>) cultivars, red leaf Sunmang' and green leaf 'Grand Rapid' 18 day seedlings for 4 weeks.	Red leaf lettuce shoots fresh weights under R and G1B1 were almost 61 percent higher than those under R and B2.	(Loi et al., 2020)
17.	UVA 315 –400 nm	<i>Lactuca sativa</i> var. <i>Crispa</i>	greater mass of new shoots	(Loi et al.2020)
18.	Green 490 – 550 nm	Red leaf lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>) 'Banchu Ref Fire'	High-intensity green light (300 mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹) promoted lettuce growth more than FL, with 510 nm light having the greatest impact on growth.	(Rahman, et al., 2021)
19.	Blue 425 – 490 nm	Non-heading Chinese cabbage (<i>Brassica campestris</i> L.)	Red and blue/red LEDs promote reproductive growth, while blue LEDs are advantageous for vegetative growth.	(Al Murad, et al., 2021)
20.	Blue 425 – 490 nm	Red leaf lettuce seedling (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> cv. Banchu Red Fire)	Compact lettuce seedling shape; encouraged lettuce development after transplanting.	(Vaštakaitė-Kairienė et al., 2021)
21.	Blue 425 – 490 nm	Red leaf lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> cv. Outeredgeous)	leaf enlargement	(Boros, et al., 2023)
22.	Far-red 700 – 850 nm	Baby leaf lettuce (<i>L. sativa</i>) 'Red Cross'	Increased leaf and stem length	(Meng, & Runkle, 2020)
23.	Far-red 700 – 850 nm	Red leaf lettuce (<i>L. sativa</i>) 'Outeredgeous	Leaf lengthening	(Mandal, 2021)
24.	Far-red 700 – 850 nm	Red leaf lettuce (<i>L. sativa</i>) 'Outeredgeous'	Increased biomass overall	(Boros et al., 2023)
25.	Far-red 700 – 850 nm	Baby leaf lettuce (<i>L. sativa</i>) 'Red Cross'	An increase in fresh weight and dry weight of the plant was observed.	(Meng, & Runkle, 2020)

The Far-red LED with a wavelength range of 700-850 nm is the most essential LED type for enhancing lettuce plants' growth and physiological aspects. It has consistently demonstrated its significance across various lettuce cultivars such as Red Lettuce, Butterhead Lettuce, Romaine Lettuce, and others. The UVA LED with a wavelength range of 315-400 nm has a relatively lower frequency of occurrence but has a specific influence on plant morphology, particularly in *Lactuca sativa* var. Crispa. However, its utilization is less prevalent than other LED types like Far-red, Blue, and Red LEDs across the studies included in the table.

Chlorophyll and Carotenoid Pigments in Lettuce Plants

The lettuce plants cultivated with B/R treatment had considerably more chlorophyll and carotenoids (Alrajhi, et al., 2023). Carotenoid levels in lettuce increased in response to red light (Duchovskis, 2021) additionally, red leaf exposed to blue light has greater antioxidant potential (Shao et al., 2020). Blue light raises the level of chlorophyll (Chen et al., 2021). Paralleled to far-red light, which reduced the concentration by 14% and 11%, white fluorescent light enhanced the concentration of carotenoid and chlorophyll. Blue light, on the other hand, raises the content of anthocyanin and carotenoid in baby leaf lettuce by 31% and 11%, respectively (Landi et al., 2022). According to studies, red lettuce exposed to a red-green light combination exhibits a discernible change in the amount of chlorophyll (Frąszczak, & Kula-Maximenko, 2021). A prolonged Light/Darkness therapy of blue/red light was observed to cause a drop in chlorophyll and carotenoid levels, followed by a rise. Lettuce plants exposed to UVA and UVB rays increase the concentration of anthocyanin (Aguirre-Becerra et al., 2020), As light intensity increases, blue/red light therapy keeps leaf greenness at a minimum (Chen et al., 2022b; Modarelli et al., 2022). The various lighting conditions utilized to develop the plants did not affect bioactive substances like carotenoids and chlorophylls (Chla and Chlb) (Camejo et al., 2020). However, plants treated with Blue, Blue/Red-LED have over 24% higher chlorophyll content compared to Red-LED, which had the lowest content among all treatments (Lee et al., 2023).

Table 2: Effect of LEDs on bioactivities of lettuce plant (Pigments)

S/N	LED Lights	Plant	Effect on Pigments	Reference
1.	Blue, Blue/Red LED	Mini Red Romaine Lettuce (cv Breed)	B, BR-LED treatment resulted in over 24% higher chlorophyll content compared to R-LED treatment.	(Lee et al., 2023)
2.	Blue/Red 259 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-2}$ Blue/Red 389 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-2}$	Red Lettuce Batavia cv (Blackhawk)	Leaf greenness reduces as light intensity rises (Chlorophyll pigments)	(Modarelli et al., 2022)
3.	Red/Blue L16/D8 L24/D12 L48/D24 L96/D48 L120/D60	Butter leaf lettuce	Chlorophyll and carotenoid levels decreased and rose over the prolonged L/D therapy.	(Chen et al., 2022b)

4.	Blue 400-500 nm Red 600-700 nm	Lettuce cultivars B. Lettony and B. Diablotin	Two Light spectrum are efficiently absorbed by chlorophyll and has no effect on bioactive substances like (Chla/Chlb)	(Camejo et al., 2020)
5.	Blue 440 nm	Lettuce (<i>L. sativa</i> var. foliosum cv. 'Dubacek' and <i>L. sativa</i> 'Michalina')	Increased chlorophyll concentration	(Gad et al., 2021)
6.	Blue/red LED	lettuce plants (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L. cv. Grizzly)	Chl a and b and Car content were significantly greater in plants grown under B/R irradiation.	(Hernández Adasme et al., 2022)
7.	UVA 315–400 nm UVB 280–315 nm	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.) 'Red fire'	Pre-harvest UV-B light stimulated concentration. With the highest concentration observed at 310 nm as compared to 325 and 340 nm.	(Santin et al., 2023)
8.	Red 620–700 nm	Lettuce (<i>L. sativa</i> var. <i>crispa</i>) Green Oak Leaf	Increased chlorophyll and carotenoids concentrations	(Leitão, 2021).
9.	Red and Green LED	Red Leaf Lettuce	LED resulted in the lowest chlorophyll levels in red leaf lettuce, despite significant variation observed.	(Alrajhi et al., 2023)
10.	UVA 315–400 nm	'Red Cross' baby leaf lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>)	Carbohydrate concentration increased	(Kelly, & Runkle, 2023)
11.	Blue 425–490 nm	Red leaf lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> Outeredgeous)	Increased concentration of vitamin c s, higher antioxidant potential	(Mandal, 2021)
12.	Blue 425–490 nm	Baby leaf lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.) 'Red Cross'	Water concentration increased by 31%. Carotenoid concentration increased by 12%	(Sawatdee et al., 2023)
13.	Far-red 700–850 nm	Baby leaf lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.) 'Red Cross'	Decreased chlorophyll and carotenoid concentration by 14% and 11% as compared to white florescent	(Vaštakaitė-Kairienė et al., 2021)

The table provided shows that Blue LED is the most commonly used LED type in plant studies. It has a wavelength range of 400-500 nm and has been used in studies on various plants such as Mini Red Romaine Lettuce, Red Lettuce Batavia, Butter leaf lettuce, lettuce cultivars B. Lettony and B. Diablotin, and more. These studies have explored the effects of Blue LED light on chlorophyll content, leaf greenness, and pigment concentrations. However, the UVA LED (315-400 nm) has limited usage. It impacts pigment levels in specific plants such as 'Red Cross' baby leaf lettuce.

Antioxidant Contents in Lettuce Plants

Vitamin C levels rise when exposed to blue light, while phenolic levels rise somewhat when exposed to blue LEDs and dramatically when exposed to white light (Shao, et al., 2021). Under red light, there was a decrease in the ascorbic acid content of lamb's lettuce (Song, et al., 2020), having a more substantial favourable impact under green light (Paradiso, & Proietti, 2022). Blue light treatment significantly raises the levels of phenolic compounds and the overall antioxidant capacity of red leaf lettuce (Samuolienė, et al.,

2021). Furthermore, when R7/B3 treatment is combined, phenolic concentration and antioxidant capacity are significantly higher than when R9B1 treatment is used, at 53–56% and 61–67%, respectively. Changing from blue to green light results in a drop in total phenolic concentration and antioxidant capability (Zhang et al., 2022). Vitamin C content in butter leaf lettuce treated with L24-D12 drops 23%. It rises as the Light/Dark time lengthens, ranging from 7.14 to 78.6% (Chen et al., 2022b) except for a small quantity of flavanol that was found in SWL 2 (romaine lettuce), red/blue treatment enhanced phenolic and flavanol concentrations in butter and romaine lettuce. It had no effect on normal white light (NWL) and specific white light (SWL) 1, however (Nguyen et al., 2021). According to this research (Lee et al., 2023), BR-led treatment is closely linked to the bitterness of lettuce, which is identified by high anthocyanin levels and leaf colour.

Table 3: Effect of LEDs on bioactivities of lettuce plant (Antioxidant)

S/N	LED Lights	Plant	Effect on Antioxidant	Reference
1.	Blue/Red LED	Mini Red Romaine Lettuce (cv Breed)	The bitterness of lettuce treated with BR-led is strongly linked to its anthocyanin concentration and leaf color.	(Lee et al., 2023)
2.	Red/Blue L16/D8 L24/D12 L48/D24 L96/D48 L120/D60	Butter leaf lettuce	L24-D12 treatment decreased Vitamin C content by 25.3%, whereas extending the L/D period increased it by up to 78.6%.	(Chen et al., 2022b)
3.	Red/Blue LED SWL1 SWL 2	Butterhead Lettuce Romaine Lettuce	RB treatment increased phenolic and flavanol concentration, except for SWL2, which had a small flavanol increase with no effect on NWL or SWL1.	(Nguyen et al., 2021)
4.	Blue LED White LED	lettuce plants (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L. cv. Grizzly)	The amount of vitamin C was increased with notable success. Additionally, phenolics increased marginally under blue LEDs and significantly under white LEDs.	(Amoozgar et al., 2017)
5.	Red and Blue LED Green LED	Red Leaf Lettuce	R7B3 LED light improved total phenolic concentration and antioxidant capacity, while replacing blue LEDs with green LEDs resulted in a decline.	(Nguyen, & Oh, 2021)
6.	Red 620 – 700 nm	Lamb’s lettuce (valerianella locusta L.) ‘Nordholland’	Reduced ascorbic acid concentration.	(Hernández, et al., 2020)
7.	Blue LEDs	Red Leaf lettuce	Blue light intensity increase raised total phenolic concentration and antioxidant capacity in red leaf lettuce.	(Mohamed, et al., 2021)
8.	Green 490 –550 nm	Red leaf ‘Multired 4’, green leaf ‘Multigreen 3’, and light green leaf ‘Multiblond 2’ baby leaf lettuce	535 nm green LEDs had greater positive effect on ascorbic acid, tocopherol contents and DPPH free-radical scavenging capacity	(Narayanan, 2020)
9.	Blue 425 – 490 nm	Red leaf lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> cv. Banchu Red Fire)	Greater polyphenol concentrations and total antioxidant status	(Sawatdee, et al., 2023)

According to the data provided, it appears that the Blue/Red LED is the most commonly utilized LED type in the studies reviewed. This LED type is frequently used in research involving Mini Red Romaine Lettuce (cv Breed), where it is closely linked to the lettuce's anthocyanin concentration and leaf colour.

Additionally, it has been shown to influence the bitterness of the lettuce (Lee et al., 2023). In contrast, the Red LED with a wavelength range of 620-700 nm is used less frequently, particularly in research involving Lamb's lettuce (*Valerianella locusta* L.) 'Nordholland.' In this study, the use of Red LED reduced ascorbic acid concentration (Sarropoulou, et al., 2022).

These findings suggest that Red LEDs have a more specific and limited use compared to the more widespread application of Blue/Red LEDs across the studies analyzed.

Effect of LED Lights on the Lettuce Nutritional Content.

Mineral Elements in Lettuce Plants

Compared to plants illuminated with red and blue light, far-red light promoted the absorption of N and K, Ca, and Mg, with the latter increasing by 27%, 25%, and 28%, respectively (Kong, & Nemali, 2021). The concentration of nitrate is reduced in all species of baby leaf lettuce and butterhead lettuce when the light is green (Sahin, & Dincer Seckin, 2022).

According to reports, lettuce cultivated under red-led illumination had significantly greater K, Fe, Zn, Cu, and Mn levels. In contrast, plants treated with blue/red and white led had substantially higher levels of N and Mg (Soufi et al., 2023). Ca²⁺ content has increased dramatically with R/B treatment in the B. Lettony cultivar, approaching 40% (Camejo et al., 2020).

The utilization of Blue/Red LEDs is prevalent in examining mineral content, particularly in Lettuce cultivar B. Lettony. They have proven incredibly effective, with an increase in Ca²⁺ content of almost 40%.

Conversely, Green LEDs are not as commonly employed but possess specific properties. For example, they have been shown to reduce nitrate concentrations in Butterhead lettuce 'De Lier' and a variety of baby leaf lettuce types such as red leaf 'Multired 4,' green leaf 'Multigreen 3,' and light green leaf 'Multiblond 2.'

Sugars Content of Lettuce Plant

According to reports, green light raises the concentration of saccharides in all cultivars of baby leaf lettuce (Fylladitakis, 2023). Additionally, red/blue treatments, except for the (L24-D12) treatment, significantly boost the amount of soluble sugar and crude fiber contents (Chen et al., 2022a).

Table 4: Effect of LEDs on nutritional contents of lettuce plant (sugar & minerals)

S/N	LED Lights	Nutrients	Plant	Effect on Nutrient Contents	Reference
1.	Red/Blue L16/D8 L48/D24 L96/D48 L120/D60	Carbohydrate	Butter leaf lettuce	The quantity of soluble sugar and crude fiber is greatly increased by all treatments, with the exception of (L24-D12)	(Chen et al., 2022b)
2.	UV-A treatment	Proteins	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>), cv. Red-leaf 'New Red Fire' and green-leaf 'Two Star'	Supplemental UV-A treatment (LED without lenses) for 6 days enhanced the amount of protein by approximately 31% in the leaves of 'New Red Fire' and by around 48% in the leaves of 'Two Star' lettuce.	(Lee et al., 2022)
3.	Green 490 – 550 nm	Sugars	Baby leaf lettuce: red leaf 'Multired 4', green leaf 'Multigreen 3' and light green leaf 'Multiblond 2'	Increase in saccharide concentrations in all baby leaf lettuce varieties	(Sharma, et al., 2024)

S/N	LED Lights	Plant	Effect on Minerals	Reference
1.	UV-A treatment	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>), cv. Red-leaf 'New Red Fire'	Longer exposure of 'New Red Fire' to supplemental UV-A LED resulted in a higher accumulation of many essential nutrients including P, K, S, Ca, and Mn compared to the control plants	(Lee et al., 2022)
2.	Blue 400-500nm Red 600-700nm	Lettuce cultivar B. Lettony	Ca ²⁺ content has significantly increased to nearly 40% under B. Lettony cultivar	(Camejo et al., 2020)
3.	Red LED Blue/Red and White LEDs	Lettuce plants (<i>Lactuca sativa L.</i> cv. Grizzly)	Lettuce grown under red LED illumination had higher levels of K, Fe, Zn, Ca, and Mn. Blue/red and white LED resulted in higher levels of N and Mg in the plants.	(Blanche, 2023)
4.	Far-red 700-850 nm	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa L.</i>) 'Frillice Crisp'	Plants absorb more N, K, Ca, and Mg when exposed to far-red light compared to red and blue light. The increase in uptake is 27%, 25%, and 28%, respectively.	(Kong, & Nemali, 2021)
5.	Green 490-550 nm	Butterhead lettuce 'De Lier'	Decreased nitrate concentrations	(Mauerer, et al., 2023)
6.	Green 490-550 nm	Baby leaf lettuce: red leaf 'Multired 4', green leaf 'Multigreen 3' and light green leaf 'Multiblond 2'	Reduced nitrate concentration in all baby leaf lettuce varieties.	(Germer, et al., 2023)

The table above shows that the Red/Blue LED combination is the most commonly used light source for increasing carbohydrate and sugar content in Butter leaf lettuce. However, the Green LED (490-550nm) is used less frequently. It has a more specialized application for increasing saccharide concentrations in certain baby leaf lettuce varieties, such as 'Multired 4,' 'Multigreen 3,' and 'Multiblond 2'.

CONCLUSION

It is important to understand that different wavelengths of light affect the growth and quality of lettuce plants. Research shows that green and blue light are particularly beneficial, as they have been proven to increase vitamin C levels and decrease nitrate levels in plants. Furthermore, incorporating red light into the lighting regimen has decreased nitrate levels and boosted vitamin C content, leading to high-quality lettuce plants. While green light positively affects growth, nitrate concentration, saccharide concentration, and vitamin C concentration, blue light positively impacts vegetative growth, pigment, and vitamin C concentration, resulting in more compact plants. However, it is essential to exercise caution when using far-red light, as excessive exposure can lead to adverse effects such as elongated plants and reduced pigment concentration.

Hydroponic lettuce cultivation is rich in nutritional benefits due to the presence of essential mineral nutrients and bioactive compounds. However, to ensure that these benefits are fully realized, it is essential to follow effective pre- and post-harvest strategies that consider the unique needs of this growing method. In hydroponic lettuce cultivation, it is crucial to use chemical nutritional solutions to meet the plant's nutritional requirements at each stage of its growth. Close monitoring and maintenance of various parameters, such as pH, electrical conductivity, temperature, and oxygen dissolved in water, are also necessary to minimize potential risks and ensure optimal growth conditions.

Plant growth and development are vital for human survival, and LED lighting has revolutionized the way we grow plants. However, the complex effects of LED lighting on plants underscore the need for comprehensive investigations. While the Blue/Red LED combination is commonly used, the less frequently utilized LEDs, including those in the far-red, white, and UVA spectrums, demonstrate specific impacts on plant morphology, pigment concentrations, and antioxidant levels.

Moreover, the varying outcomes in nutrient content under different LED types highlight the complexity of plant-nutrient interactions. These nuances suggest potential opportunities to optimize plant growth and nutritional value under different LED lighting conditions. Therefore, further research is justified to enhance our understanding of the optimal light conditions for various plant species, their specific physiological outcomes, and their nutritional contents. By investing in this research, we can increase the efficiency and sustainability of plant growth, which will benefit both our environment and our health.

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